

CONTEMPORARY CHALLENGES AND ISSUES BEFORE THE PRESENT
TEACHER EDUCATION SYSTEM OF INDIA
IN THE ERA OF GLOBALIZATION

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Abstract

Education and especially teacher education is undergoing rapid and constant changes under the effects of globalization. The term globalization means integration of economies and societies through cross-country flows of information, ideas, technologies, services, capital, finance and people encompassing the entire globe. It is claimed that globalization marks akin to a small village through time and space. Understanding of these new technologies being an important facilitator of this interconnectivity. Globalization has resulted in significant changes in the knowledge economy and has ushered new conditions for the process of teacher education to cater the skill requirement all across the globe. Due to globalization, the total education system is now available under one roof. Globalization has impacted teacher education from all the sides. Teacher education today is no more constrained by geographical boundaries. The key elements in globalization include the knowledge society, Information and communication technologies, the market economy, trade liberalization and changes in governance structure. These elements of globalization have impacted significantly in the education sector in general and teacher education in particular. The present paper critically examines and makes a humble attempt to describe the effect of globalization in teacher education. The author in the present paper also highlights upon the meeting problem and issues being faced in the present teacher education system of India, in the context of globalization.

Key words: *Globalization, Information society, International influence, Knowledge*

Economy, Trade in education services, Teacher Education Development

Introduction

Globalization is a process, which has affected many areas of human life, one of those being teacher education. In common term, globalization is the process by which an activity or undertaking becomes world wide in scope. Globalization is defined as increased permeability of traditional boundaries of almost every kind, including physical borders such as time, space, nation states and economies, industries and organizations and less tangible borders such as cultural norms. At the moment, globalization is a buzz word on everyone's lips. UNCTAD defines, "the concept of globalization refers to both an increasing flow of goods and services and resources across national borders to the emergence of complementary set of organizational structure to manage expanding network of international economic activity and transaction". Knight and De-Wit¹⁴ defines it as, "the flow of technology, economy, knowledge, people, values and ideas across borders. Globalization affects each country in a different way due to nation's individual history, traditions, culture and priorities". Globalization and rewarding change to the teacher systems of the developed countries, where as for the developing countries, where the system is facing the scarcity of resources, it threatens the stability needed to build the well performing system. Developing countries often have to adjust willingly or unwillingly both to the quickening pulse of international change and accordingly reform on several fronts simultaneously, which may not be possible under the given resource status of teacher education. It is argued in the literature, that impact of globalization has been significant on the economies of both developing and developed nations. All of their governmental systems are believed to be affected by the various process of globalization. The focus in this present paper is on globalization and its impact on teacher education system in the present Indian scenario.

Globalization though has contributed for rise in living standards, improvement in health and education and technology advancement, especially in the area of communication and computers during this period, yet in the recent past, there have been apprehensions expressed in terms of its impact, especially in the people who still live below the poverty line. The thrust of globalization is expected to push teacher education to face far-reaching challenges. According to the Spanish sociologist, Manuel Castells, one of the leading authorities on globalization states, "effects of globalization on the university education will be more drastic than industrialization, urbanization and secularization combined. It is the

biggest challenge that the university has ever faced for more than a century a half". John Smyth, (1996)¹³ argues, "the globalization of world capitalism has had significant impact on teacher education policy and produced change in the sector. In particular, globalization has caused a major restructuring of the economy and government has reacted within a corporatist and technocratic framework to create new technology-based industries. This has created moves to reform teacher education in order to produce the necessary teacher educators. This strategy will not succeed; and that when it fails, higher education will be the scapegoat."

Thus, globalization is affecting all spheres of life through scientific and technological revolution. Shrinking time and disappearing boundaries are the three distinctive features of globalization (Human Development Report by UNDP, 1999)³². Globalization has a multi-dimensional impact on teacher education. It has increased the need for reforms in teacher education with particular reference to large-scale of utilization of Information technology and more emphasis on research and developmental activities.

Globalization and Education

Globalization has a close relation with education. As education has an important place in shaping a society, it has to be connected with globalization and global activities have a deep impact on education. Globalization of world economies is leading to increased emphasis on internationalization of the teacher education curriculum. It also contributes to opportunities for new partnerships in research and teaching with agencies and institutions across the globe (Twigg & Blinger, 1996)³⁰. Globalization symbolizes a paradigm shift involving the re-thinking of beliefs and structures in traditional consciousness. It symbolizes a shift from mono-cultural approach to teacher education to multi-cultural approach. Globalization is one of the several powerful worldwide forces that are transforming the basis of business competition, paradoxically harkening an eras in which small, local communities of practice may become a permanent structural form. Communities of practice enable organizations to build, share and apply the deep level of competence-required to complete in a knowledge-based global economy (Drucker, 1993)⁴. With the concept of globalization, a lot of changes are expected in the field of teacher education. In an era of globalization, it appears 'change' seems to become a permanent future of human civilization. Thus, the cultivation of a permanent learning attitude and disposition becomes a major mission of teacher educational institutions (TEIs), all over the world. The skills and competencies needed for survival in the era of globalization, perhaps call for the adoption of more innovative approaches to teacher

education. Embedded in such innovative approaches are features such as effective use of technology in teaching, reflective intergenerational dialogue, performance-based learning activities and other inter-professional interactive and collaborative approaches to delivery of school instructions. One of the main duties of schools is to enhance the individuals' appropriateness for the rapid changes. As Benking (1997)³ remarks, today universities and other institutions are redoubling their efforts to respond to social change. They have to implement society's expectations. Gordon (1999)⁹ outlines the importance of higher education in the learning society by attributing the report of the National Committee of Inquiry into higher education, in the following words: "Higher education is fundamental to the social, economic and cultural health of the nation. It will contribute not only through the intellectual development of students and by equipping them for work, but also by adding to the world's store of knowledge and understanding, fostering culture for its own sake and promoting the values, that characterize higher education: respect for evidence, respect for individuals and their views and the search for truth. Equally, part of its task will be to accept a duty of care for the well being of our democratic civilization, based on respect for the individual and respect by the individual for the conventions and laws which provide the basis of a civilized society".

Future universities and other institutions are not thought only for the young. They are expected to become more open to all people of all ages who wish to further their education. Universities and other teacher training institutions will be open to anyone who has acquired the motivation to learn and the ability to perceive issues through social experience or involvement in volunteer and other activities. Besides, an increase in the number of students, both part-time and full-time, is expected and this is through to lead to the formation of an academic environment with greater depth. Graduate study is also likely to become more available to non academic members of society. As higher education is an investment in progress and prosperity, during rapid social and economic change, it is especially important that universities and other institutions of higher education should reconsider their contribution to society from a broad, long-term perspective.

Impact of Globalization and Teacher Education

Education in general and teacher education in particular, is undergoing constant changes under the effect of globalization. The effects of globalization on teacher education has brought rapid developments in the field of technology and communications.

Globalization in the perspective of teacher education, implies a process of cultural, educational, scientific and technological integration. The rise of global society, driven by technology and communications developments are shaping children, the future citizens of the world into 'global citizens', intelligent people with a broad range of skills and knowledge to apply to a competitive, information based society.

The future of country often lies within their ability to compete in a global market, where industrial based-economies are giving way to knowledge-based industries, realising the importance of, "knowledge, skills and the intellectual capacity to meet the challenges of accelerated change and uncertainty". Education is becoming a life-long learning and training process, developing transferable skills and knowledge, that can be applied to competitive markets where knowledge and information is being traded as a commodity. The introduction of technology into classroom is changing the nature of delivery education to students and is gradually giving way to a new form of electronic literacy, more programs and education, materials are made available in electronic form, teachers are preparing material in electronic form; and students are generating papers, assignments and projects in electronic form. The landscape of the present teacher education and teaching in general is being reconfigured, as blackboards are now being replaced by Video projection and screens, books with storage device servers and CD ROMs and through on-line digital libraries. Even exams and grades are gradually becoming available through electronic means and notebooks are starting to give way to laptops. Also, students can be examined through computer-managed learning systems and do tutorial exercises on a computer rather than in a classroom. Such developments in education portray that there had been shift from industrialization to information-based societies. Subsequently, technology is foreseeing a change in the education environment towards a reliance on electronic sources to deliver material. With such changes and the emergence of video-conferencing and the Internet, the barriers of distance are being broken down at a rapid rate, due to the key aspect of globalization.

The rapid growth of television services, with their immense influence as media of mass communication, has been very relevant in the technological shift. Other large contributions to this shift include the transistor and space satellites. Communication and information-based technology over the years is the Internet, which is a massive network of computers located throughout the world. These computers maintain libraries of text, images, computer software, and other forms of data that can be accessed by anyone, anywhere, at any

time. This implementation of technology and communication to be a successful venture and to educate a society, both students and teachers need to be technologically literate.

Communication technology is offering new challenges for students of all abilities as they can discuss issues of concern with their fellow students from around the world, thus developing communication and interpersonal skills, fostering a mutual understanding across countries and cultures. Students are themselves discovering knowledge through inquiry and experimentation rather than memorizing facts in a teacher dominated classroom setting. In fact, students no longer need to be physically present to learn as education material is becoming readily available over the Internet, through video conferencing, and tape recordings. Institutions are now turning the use of Internet to deliver courses to students. A shift in the paradigm of education is becoming evident where more responsibility is being placed on the individual for his or her learning, instead of solely on the teacher. Subsequently, the teachers themselves also need to be highly technologically literate, needing the competence and confidence to prepare students for a global information society.

There are several forces behind the globalization of teacher education; some of them are as given below:

1. With generalization of higher education, there is sudden demand for higher education that cannot be met by most governments on their own and therefore globalization is the natural choice.
2. Creates scope for business-academia interface and exposure to work scenario in future.
3. Exposes to latest educational technology and practical insights.
4. A large demand of teachers is likely to come from developing nations. These nations lack resources and hence greatly rely on the foreign countries; whereas western countries are resource abundance and desire to have trading partnerships.
5. In the wake of knowledge-based and technology-driven economies, it is necessary for nation's to upgrade people's skills constantly. Expansion of teacher education is the last resort as it helps in capacity building, human resource development, practical and relevant

education, professional training, broadening one's outlook, acceptance of multiculturalism, ethnic or linguistic diversities, etc.

6. It is proved by the studies that education level corresponds to living standard of the beholder. Aspiration of living a good life eventually forced people to rush for higher education. Some countries do not have adequate infrastructure to fulfil the need, whereas, some countries are in a position to supply the services of higher education to demanding countries.

7. Being the greatest beneficiary of the economic growth led by talented pool, private sector is willing to invest into teacher education and professional training of teachers more than the States do.

8. The scientific and technological background plays a supremely important role in carrying education across the border.

Teacher education, in this situation, assumes greatest significance from two perspectives. One is coping with the globalization forces and other is guiding the globalization towards preferred course of objective.

Teachers and their Training in the Era of Globalization

The main focus of teachers training should depart from the traditional methods of professional teacher educational program which thus far has not produced the desired quality and professionalism. This system exposes the teacher to acquire a body of knowledge in a subject discipline. He/she takes courses in education, which involves methodology of teaching learning. Lastly, he/she should go through a supervised teaching practice which is referred to as apprentice. This system has not produced the desired result for a Transformative educational system in a globalized world, innovation required for both for teacher pre-service preparation and teacher in-service training. It is for this reason, the school-based teacher professional preparation and development is advocated. This enables

schools and teachers to play a much larger role in teacher's professional development. This will eventually make the schools be the first to reap the benefits of generation of good teachers. The cluster school-based teacher in-service teacher development is an innovation being carried out. It is a system of mentoring whereby teacher's educators or professional teachers support teachers directly in their classrooms with intensive period of mentoring and discussion in teachers' meetings within the schools and across a cluster of schools to develop reflective practices and reflective practitioners. The goal of global competitiveness, demands that both the curriculum and the teaching methods to be more focused on developing generic and altitudinal skills, such as critical thinking and problem solving as well as promoting national reconciliation(M.Young,1998)¹⁶.

There has been a severe shortage of teachers, particularly at the level of higher education. Economic growth led by industrial and service sector during the last few decades has created more opportunities and faster career growth for the young talent. Further, the lucrative salaries and glamour has acted as a catalyst in attracting talent to such fast growing sectors. Teacher education in India has been passing through transition on account of privatization and with drawl of financial support from the government has been finding it difficult to attract adequate number of young talent to teaching job. It is big challenge for teacher education sector to sustain in future due to lack of availability of faculty.

In order to meet the demand of technological skilled, communicative, lifelong learner teachers, we will be requiring a new way of teachers training which could be done in the following way:-

1. The rapidly increasing technological advancement and the exponential growth of

knowledge will create the environment of continuous and selective learning. The training given long before the actual job, will not remain feasible for the practical conditions.

The methods taught two or three years back will become outdated and will not be useful for the applicability of real-life situations for another few years.

2. Regular and updated on-job-training will only be suitable in case of world of mass

knowledge and technological advancement. The competent teachers of tomorrow will become stagnant or push back by their colleagues, if they deprive themselves from

updating their knowledge that is rapidly increasing and improving.

3. Loosing time in the fast growing and progressing world of knowledge and technology, will mean losing the race of life and survival. Thus, any training which is not in line with the updated information will become wastage of time.
4. Like skills, linkage of knowledge, logical approach, system thinking, experimentation, abstraction and collaboration will be getting most importance in the future teacher's training, than subject knowledge and educational theories.

Vehicles of Globalization of Teacher Education

It may include teacher education by public/private and not-for profit /for profit providers. Though small in scale, it has bigger impact than for-profit teacher education. It can take various forms ranging from face to face implementation of teacher education to e-learning.

- With technological innovations it is now possible to deliver teacher education and other technical and vocational skills on anytime, anywhere basis.
- E-learning, has made teacher education accessible, equitable, affordable, relevant and self-paced.
- It can move across the borders through franchising, twinning or launching of branch campuses at the local level.
- Establishment of Virtual universities. The term "virtual university" characterizes an organization that provides teacher education on the internet.
- Government sponsored educational programme can be run in foreign countries with an aim to enhance cultural exchanges.

Favourable effects of Globalization on Teacher Education

Process of globalization has been carrying several effect for the people, out of which following few can be cited as promising great advantages provided the people at receiving end are capable to utilize their benefits:

1. Unification of teacher education will lead to better global expansion. Quality will improve substantially and students at lower level of social strata will benefit more.

2. Conforming the supply-demand theory of trade, the students from all around the world will have easy access to teacher education.
3. Quality of teacher education will improve following the amalgamation of universities on world-wide level.
4. Courses will be diversified and students would have greater choices to select those according to aptitude and interests.
5. The phenomenon of economy of scale may bring down the cost of education to minimum level and this may benefit poor countries.
6. International standards of education can be given definite shape, regulatory framework can be further strengthened.
7. Scope of information and communication technology will be enhanced and it will squarely benefit the students irrespective of their nationality, caste and skin.
8. Research and development may scale new heights and benefits of innovation can be transferred to lowest strata.
9. Better delivery system of teacher education will reduce the cost and would enable economically poor students to get benefited.
10. Globalization of teacher education will enhance mobility of teachers and therefore bring the homogeneity in teaching quality.
11. Cultural, scientific and technological integration may lead to economic uniformity.
12. Better systems of examination, evaluation and testing will replace outdated and desirable system.

Challenges Posed by Globalization to Teacher Education System in India

The economic reforms and its outgrowth, transnational teacher education, undoubtedly pose challenges to policy makers and educationalists in the country. Unless they make the present teacher education globally competitive, competent and compatible in line with the global changes, it will be imminent that the capacity of teacher education to produce right kind of teachers would get jeopardized.

The globalization mostly benefits cities. It has been observed that a few packets of geographical locations like Hyderabad, Chennai, Pune, Noida, Delhi and regions around NCR (National Capital Region), Bangalore received significant investment. These cities are no exception to the fact that teacher education responds to the every action of globalization resulting in mushrooming of Teacher Educational Institutes in these cities (Mohan, 2008)¹⁸. As a result, the imbalance created between the cities and remote areas has becoming alarmingly dangerous. The digital and education divide and increased migration had sadly blocked the youth of Indian villages to avail of advantages of globalization particularly the sophisticated teacher education and research facilities.

The increasing number of students looking to Australia, Britain and the US for their Under-Graduate and Post Graduate programmes reveals that the educational and research institutes in the country continues to lag behind the expected qualities as there is no quicker adoption of technology and methodology in the teaching and learning process coupled with the inadequate infrastructural facilities. The failure in retaining talented students at the home institutes may cause brain drain posing serious problems to the anticipated double digit growth. Indian colleges and teacher educational institutions, with just a few exceptions, have become large, under-funded, ungovernable institutions. At many of them, politics has intruded into campus life, influencing academic appointments and decisions across levels. Under-investment in libraries, information technology, laboratories and classrooms makes it very difficult to provide top-quality instruction or engage in cutting-edge research (Malisa, Mark, 2007)¹⁷.

The rise in the number of part-time teachers and the freeze on new full-time appointments in many places has affected morale in the academic profession. The lack of accountability means that teaching and research performance of teachers is seldom measured. The system provides few incentives to perform. Bureaucratic inertia hampers change. Nevertheless, with a semblance of normalcy, faculty administrators are able to provide

teaching, coordinate examinations, and award degrees. It has been found that many Indian Institute of Technology graduates, who are well trained in technology, have decided not to contribute their skills to the burgeoning technology sector in India. Perhaps half of them leave the country immediately after their graduation so as to pursue advanced study abroad—and most of them do not return. A recent study found that, almost 86% of students in science and technology fields from India who have obtained degrees from United States do not return home immediately following their study.

The following are some of the problems that our present teacher education system is facing at the grass root level. These are:

1. It is good to educate students in their own language. But the problem is that students are supplied those translated books which are old and not up-to-date and also obsolete. To keep pace with the fast developing world it is necessary to get hold of new knowledge which can be supplied through new books.
2. Some sections of teachers involved in teaching are in teacher education system are lacking in intellectual interest and are not enough to motivate students to acquire more improved knowledge and find out the talents and potentials within students. A section of teachers does not even go through the motions of a formal lecture. They generally dictate from fragile notes. Are these type of teachers be able to guide the present generation of students in the era of globalization?
3. Our teacher education system lacks in global talents to teach, to do research and to import better knowledge along with domestic teachers. It is important that international experience would certainly add more weight to the quality of teacher education system of India.
4. Majority of students at the level of university and colleges have engaged themselves in copying notes rather than to go and read books in the university libraries.

Hence, large holdings of university libraries go unread, expensive journals remain untouched.

5. Many of our high level university people have their sights fixed on high prestige foreign models. They try to keep pace with other high level people abroad while failing to identify critical conditions of national development.
6. In the age of globalization, it is very important to feed the students the up-to-date knowledge and information. The syllabus is outdated which lacks in synchronizing appropriately with the new information.
7. Due to large number of youths entering the teacher education system, it is not possible for the existing teacher educational institutions to place these growing numbers with a healthy student-teacher ratio. Hence, there is need for more institutions of higher learning not to produce only degree-flourishing horde rather provide youths the capacity to keep pace with modern technology by giving them training in right direction.
8. In a developing country like India, most of the teacher training institutions are not equipped with modern technological machineries. The high cost of setting up new connections, low levels of technological awareness etc are some of the obstacles towards strengthening the teacher education system of India.
9. Most important is that most of the degrees given by these teacher training institutions are not locally as well as globally recognized and the institutes themselves are not accredited to give these degrees. Thus, cross-country accreditation of degrees requires a major thrust.

Some other Challenges posed to the Teacher Education System in wake of Globalization

India has now recognised that the new global scenario poses unprecedented challenges for the present teacher education system. These challenges which globalization would be able to tackle in an effective way are:

1. Challenge of Poverty and Population

Issues pertaining to poverty and population cannot be ignored, and thus this responsibility has to be taken up by teacher education. This problem is, he newly emerging interest groups in many developing countries which do not always reflect or express the needs of the poor, making it difficult for them to organize and have their opinions heard.

2. Environment

Governments need the right incentives, organizational structures and capacities to raise financial resources for protecting natural resources and enforcing environmental protection regulations. Over the past few years this subject is persistently getting ridiculed in the hands of world leadership. The teacher education has crucial contributions to other areas of environmental protection:

- Educating young people, indigenous peoples and their communities.
- Strengthening the role of NGOs.
- Educating farmers and providing them with incentives to conserve the environment.

3. Inequality

Inequality in the form of wages and salary is treading an irreversible path. This problem needs equal and immediate attention as received by lack of employment. A worker in India may be hired for as low as ten rupees per day whereas the same labour may cost a few thousand rupees in developed countries. Within, India the inequality of wages is surprisingly very high. One may commonly find teachers in private degree colleges being paid as low as 500-1000 rupees per month. It is highly intolerable to see another person in similar profession getting 40-50,000 rupees. Why this situation cannot be dealt by higher education is left unnoticed by many states? Before the forces of globalization distort the situation to irreparable extent, the teacher education should necessarily deal with strange dichotomy and ensure that people across the world fetch equal remuneration for equal work.

4. Economic Growth and Sustainability

Economic growth is a means to sustainable human development, and not an end in itself as it has been largely considered by nation states. The blind and mad race must have an end at the earliest. Human Development Report 1996 showed that economic growth does not automatically lead to sustainable human development and the elimination of poverty. For

example, many countries, including India, are showing contrasting figures for economic development indexes.

5. Empowerment

The expansion of men and women's capabilities and choices increases their ability to exercise those choices free of hunger, want and deprivation. It also increases their opportunity to participate in, or endorse, decisions making affecting their lives.

6. Co-operation and Equity

With a sense of belonging important for personal fulfilment, well-being and a sense of purpose and meaning, human development is concerned with the ways in which people work together and interact. The expansion of capabilities and opportunities means equity more than income. Teacher education is duty bound to keep intact the objective of equity even in the face of globalization.

7. Positive Approach for Indigenous Culture

It is true that ongoing process of globalization is heavily influenced with western culture; however, our right oppositions to it marks blankness of own values and culture. Teacher education may help develop consciousness in natives for our own values and culture and make them more relevant in the midst of globalization.

Globalization--- A Challenge or an Opportunity

Two of the strategic and long-term questions that globalization poses to the higher education and teacher education in particular are: (a) 'Commodification'- the use of knowledge as a purchasable and saleable good. (b) 'Alternative providers' with a profit motive of higher education's landscape that are engaged in the transmission of knowledge using Information and Communication Technologies. Displacing and reinterpreting knowledge raise fundamental questions to the Universities, more, so, in the area of autonomy and academic freedom. They also pose questions with regard to the very objectives of Higher Education system in terms of its ethical obligation to make knowledge freely available to those who seek for it. The apprehension is, that the globalization, may herald a basic change in the very role that universities that play in the society. Defying universities simply as 'service providers' and changing their responsibility to the society for the shorter gains, may in the long run, ruin the very objectives with which the universities were established(Guy,

Neave,2001)¹⁰. The dynamics of globalization is no doubt a challenge as well as an opportunity.

Teacher education today, globalization or no globalization, is no more constrained by geographical boundaries. Innovative forms of translocation and transnational education have become a possibility. Multi campus institutions, “franchised institutions learning centres providing university degree, off campus education, distance learning, internet based distance education, virtual universities merging of part studies to combine into a whole for obtaining national as well as international degrees are only few models as examples. As far as teacher education is concerned, an enthused and well-informed student has umpteen choices, for the first time in the history of education, to access for a “global market”. Yet, the matter of the fact is, this access remains only as availability. Who can reach to it and how? What alternative provision are made for those who cannot afford to reach is the crux of the matter.

Globalization- Is it a Real Challenge or Simply a Hoax?

Under the prevailing global forces, teacher education institutions everywhere are subject to global trends. Universities now facing more challenges than ever before, the rise of a globalised knowledge-based economy has brought universities in many countries under closer scrutiny for the economic contributions they make. Under the impact of globalising market forces, there has been a general trend towards the reduction of per capita public funding to teacher education, at a time when the system is still expanding at both the initial and the ‘life-long learning’ levels. The linkage of performance to allocation of operation funds leads to intense competition among universities. Associated with that is the move to privatisation of teacher education.

The current globalization of teacher education creates both challenges and opportunities. The relationship between teachers’ education and globalization gives special attention. Teacher education will be the answer to many problems raised by globalization. Educational goals are seen to be area of great concern in the era of globalization. It is here that universities play a crucially important role, for creating a better society. It is impossible to ignore the global; universities and teacher educational institutions need to reflect on the impact of globalization. They must engage with the issues of globalization, both theoretically as analysts and researchers, and practically as academic workers involved in an increasingly globalised enterprise.

As a result of globalization the opportunities in India in the field of teacher education now, appears to be immense, and areas are diverse. The remarkable development in Information Technology has promoted learners' method of learning in both formal and distance modes. Globalization is simply putting 'the space-time compression' (Scott, 1998)²³ which brings together nations, cultures, economies and at the same time increasing Inter-dependency. Interaction is expected to improve the quality of education. Imparting Teacher education through distance education and virtual institutions, that is commonly regarded to be an industrialised form of education, is now taking place in India, which is proving to be more cost effective. With one global world, the aspiring students who are left out and failed to secure their seats in India's premiere Institutions can now go abroad to fulfil their aspirations. With the fast growing Information and Communication Technology the availability and flow of academic resource materials is providing input to the academicians to compete with their counterparts any where in the world.

It assists in avoiding of duplicity in research and inspires the Indian academicians for research and publications on issues that are of International significance, in order to make their mark in their respective disciplines. The envisioned policy reform has facilitated in opening up space for establishment of private teacher educational institutes, easing and eliminating research restrictions, entry of graduate students, encouragement for foreign collaboration" in the university sector and joint ventures in an academic activities as it now exists in private industries. System-wide teacher education reform and incremental approach to liberalization of teacher education may help India to take advantage of opportunities in the new global environment. Policy makers in India might have to be concerned with increasing adult participation in continuing education and training, particularly in relation to enhanced employability (Stromquist, 2000)²⁴. It is expected to facilitate new International orders centring on life-long learning and the "learning society".

Globalization, as a process has given importance to decentralized educational governance and control. The centre has viewed decentralization as a way to increase efficiency by giving more responsibility to local level functionaries, which in turn is expected to increase motivation and accountability. Further it is trying to involve the local community in the very planning and decision-making process of education and making them responsible for "the state of the art". Internet, as an interactive medium has a potential of global reach. It has the capacity to bring knowledge and prosperity to isolated and marginalized individuals and nations. But unequal access to the Internet, the "Digital divide", creates inequity that

exacerbates other inequities. No developing country has benefited more from the digital revolution than India, and in no country is the digital divide wider or deeper. On the other side of the digital divide are the 45% of the population who cannot read or write, 44% who survive on less than Rs.50 per day, and those who live in the 370,000 villages where there is no telephone connections.

As part of the liberalization policy, it has been suggested that education should be progressively privatized and that access to it should be made subject to the payment of appropriate prices. The government, therefore, encourages the establishment of a large number of private institutions and even private universities are being encouraged. Simultaneously, mechanisms to cater to the needs of those who cannot afford payment of high fees are also being evolved. The process and effects of economic and cultural globalization are becoming evident in our educational programmes and are expressed by teachers and students with particular reference to the ways in which the global media (such as television media and internet) are deployed in the construction of knowledge. The threat is possibility of erosion of national values by imbibing the alien culture. The changes that are taking place in the country, even at the bottom level of the country; there seems to be a shift in the power relations and consciousness at various levels of civil societies. The macro change brought by International capital, technology and mass media has brought new culture, but to what extent the new cultural assertions of identity will enable the people of various regions to face the new capitalist order, remains to be seen. The threat is for national cultural values.

In India, during the period of globalization, much of the contemporary thought has gone into the issues of programmed learning, multimedia teaching, macro-micro-teaching, distance learning and other problems related to curriculum. No subject has been so much neglected as has been done to the development of humanistic values, creativity, cultural, moral and spiritual dimensions in the teaching-learning process. The threat is for the erosion of rich and old culture of human values. The ideologies of the states and of multinational agencies brought the technological revolution. The process has been promoted by the transport system, communication network, and it has increased the economic activity, but globalization does not necessarily result in homogenizations; on the contrary, it is leading to the strengthening of the ethnic identities both at local and regional levels (M.Bottery, 2006)¹⁵.

Apprehensions from Globalization

Though globalization offers us an opportunity to benefit in several ways, it also poses many threats to our educational and cultural; values. Our social sciences, humanities and literature are likely to be affected adversely by the commercial considerations in the profit-driven market. As competition becomes acute, institutions and corporate houses resort to vulgar and unethical ways. Global competition will erode our traditions and cultural heritage. The government of India has formulated several schemes for the benefit of weaker sections in the society, such as reservation for poor, backward and physically challenged students. Globalization affects each country in different ways, as nations have “different history, traditions, cultural values and priorities”, (Knight, J & de Wit, 1999)¹⁴. In the long run, globalization would increasingly result in similarities of outlook and values. It will ‘homogenize’ educational systems. As David Orr²¹ points out, “Western education, through out the world, has replaced indigenous forms of education and prepares students exclusively for an urban existence”. Our universities should protect contents from Indian culture and determined by local needs as well as for global requirements. Sharma (2003)²⁴ has also echoed similar views, “the presence of foreign universities would undermine our task of services to the community”.

Under the prevailing circumstances, the India’s elite institutions and their capacity to attract and retain world-class faculty and students in the face of attractive offers from foreign universities, research institutes and multi-national corporations is the main issue. The apprehension that haunts the Indian mind is that universities and students in India might be the losers in the game of global higher education. If globalization is taken to be a real opportunity for India and is able to benefit significantly for the global revolution in higher education, then it would require major policy reforms with regard to university structure; function, structure-function relation, funds and the way universities are regulated. It would require closer links between industries and institutions especially in the growing technology-based sectors, and an entrepreneurial style of leadership to head the Indian universities. Given these inputs, India might be able to capture the benefits of globalization. No doubt, the country has potential and individuals are capable, yet, “ifs and buts” appear to be the crux of the matter. The matter is “how to achieve the concrete gains from existing higher education system as well as from the present teacher education system, competing with Global trends

without sacrificing National goals of higher education and development and without abandoning its commitment to Indian tradition and cultural values.

With liberalization of the country's economy, global market forces have generated new fears and dilemmas for the present teacher education system in India. In order to take advantage of the low cost of educated labour, multinationals have been locating many of their labour-intensive operations here. Education, and especially teacher education is being commercialized which may in turn penalize the participation of brilliant students coming from poor background. In Nation building, an overwhelming emphasis on commercialization and competition also involves risk of undermining the inculcation of higher values of sacrifice, service and commitment to the country, a loss that may be difficult to overcome; it may contribute for materialism and self-centredness converting students towards self-centred personality.

Globalization is also likely to impact negatively our rural-urban divide. This will increase differences in terms of income and culture between rural and urban population. Globalization will also tempt our best faculty to go abroad for more lucrative jobs. Our best institutions are already working with depleted strength. The developing countries have an intuitive feeling that many of the WTO policies such as regarding patents are clearly designed to benefit the western countries. With their superior technology and infrastructure, the foreign education providers will only exploit the developing countries to earn maximum profit.

Suggestions and Educational Implications for Teacher Education

As cited by Dubey, S.C., 1998¹⁸, "Teacher education in India will have to adopt and promote the values of democracy, egalitarianism, social justice and secularism. More than these, it must emphasize excellence, high performance and problem solving". In modern technical age our youths should prepare to take new path for living with a design aiming at sustainable development of the whole country. Indian higher education has to help in this direction only by accustoming them with proper skill and knowledge. Therefore, to strengthen teacher education system of India, by making it compatible in this age of globalization, some following steps must be undertaken:-

1. Firstly, we have to identify the objective of our teacher education system. It is necessary to make the Indian teacher education an instrument of producing skilled youths with talents and capabilities to solve problems.

2. Secondly, we should choose proper guide to provide guidance to the youngsters of the nation and prepare them to face the world with their skill and knowledge. Hence, there should be scope to train the teachers with new technologies and make them good enough to guide the students. They must constantly update their knowledge base on the teaching methods. As, for example in Geography syllabus GIS is a recent addition and in the same way in Computers subject, "Data-mining", is the latest addition to every University and higher education syllabus, whereas the teachers are not good enough to teach their students these new technologies.

3. Thirdly, all the teacher educational institutions must prepare the course-work with changing contexts of life and according to national needs rather follow foreign models. We have to give our students a realistic feeling for the science-based, new information based and modern technology oriented rapidly changing society of tomorrow. Concepts of remedial classes are not new. But the feedbacks should be given more emphasis.

4. Fourthly, we have to take some hared decisions in the admission procedure of the huge number of students to teacher educational institutions. It is our duty to provide proper training to all those who do not enter the system of teacher education so that they find the right employment in their life by increasing their capability.

5. Fifthly, we must evolve an effective strategy for the management of teacher education institutions. The turmoil within the teacher education management affects negatively upon the students.

6. Sixthly, it is important to invest values and commitment into the system of teacher education of the country. Otherwise the very purpose of teacher education will be defeated.

Conclusion

The purpose of globalization of Indian teacher education is to make major sources of earning foreign exchange; to improve quality of Indian education and to spread Indian culture and value. Setting uyp units abroad will create awareness about Indian teacher education system, but it will not help us to earn a substantial amount of foreign exchange because a major portion would be spent to run the teacher training institutions. Hence, looking at the purpose, of various options of globalization of Indian education, the most appropriate option would be to attract the maximum possible number of foreign students. Globalization of teacher education is to promoted and social advantages that accrue from the presence of

international students on campuses. Teacher training institutions must re-engineer their vision and mission to carryout multinational activities. The teacher trainings institutions must withstand the challenges of globalization. Globalization does not necessarily mean that every country starts following the footprints of western economy, culture and education. Why not India teachers the whole world the meaning of “*Vasudhaiv Kutumbakam*” and why not it devises means to spread education of humanity? Our teacher education should be prepared in such a way that it could take real challenges of the contemporary times into acknowledgement and respond to in a rational manner.

Today all the teacher educational institutions are feeling the heat of globalization and are under some sort of pressure from forces which promote globalization and globalized culture. Teachers in India, whether they are in private or government are facing stiff competition from foreign campuses which are establishing their centres in India, as they are providing their students with latest methodologies and technologies in teaching and learning and an high quality infrastructure. While there is deterioration the quality of teacher training institutions in India, the foreign universities are providing high quality in the delivery of their educational services. Teaching is a profession, which requires expert knowledge and specialised skills, acquired and maintained through rigorous and continuing study. It also calls for a sense of personal and corporate commitment to the education and welfare of the students. A teacher has many roles to perform. Roles of a teacher are not static but dynamic as these continuously change as per the demands of the society. Various policies also limit or extend the scope of these roles. World is positive about its potential for economic and political progress in the 21st century. The trends and characteristics of globalization perhaps call for a total re-invention or revamping of the whole teaching profession. The teacher in the globalized environment must be prepared to think globally and act locally in matters relating to teacher education. He must be able to create a learning, friendly and animating envrioenmt in the classroom. The teachers must be able to participate effectively in the contemporary ICT imposed revolution in knowledge creation, distribution and management. Schools exist to impart knowledge and skills. It is therefore imperative for schools to move with time in matters relating to knowledge creation and distribution. The current state of Teacher training institutions on ICT should be improved as a priority and national emergency. Teacher education policies and practices also need a fundamental overhaul in order to ensure that modern teachers are produced from teacher training institutions. Computer training and information technology must be central components in teacher preparation programs. The

ideal teacher in a globalized world must be an expert in a subject area as well as an expert in the use of Information and technology in teaching learning situations. Such teacher must be prepared to be active participants in integrated communities of learners. This is so because in an era of globalization, boundaries between institutions and homes, societies and institutions, between different disciplines and spheres of knowledge are bound to disappear and be replaced by integrated communities of learners. Motivation and productivity among teachers will disappear in teacher training institutions that do not anchor teachers' promotions on the performance of individual teachers. Ministry of Education in countries need to radically change their teachers' promotion policy if they are sincerely interested in keeping a teaching manpower with high morale for a globalized society that is perennially on the move for positive changes.

Thus, to conclude it could be said that, there is a need to examine the relevance of teacher education in a conceptual framework for the long term, medium term and short term goals, in terms of jobs and career, specific challenges in life consisting of event management or crisis management, etc and with regard to societal values, individual values, cultural aspects and situations of non-neutrality of individual values. Developing countries must ensure that their teacher training institutions are able to participate in economic and social development and take advantage of globalization. They must build a political system that encourages government, political, business and civic leaders to articulate and pursue objectives that are centred around people and a system that promotes public consensus on these objectives. Innovative researches must be done at the level of teacher education and the training of teachers, both in-service and pre-service, so that it should enable to decipher the inter-linkages and connections between several dimensions of globalization and the existing policies of the present teacher education system in India. Teacher education system will not be modernized until the whole system of teacher training both at in-service and pre-service is drastically overhauled and made intellectually richer, and more challenging.

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